

The etiology of red stripe of rice: current status and future directions

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Red stripe is an emerging disease* of the rice crop that has been observed in recent years in intensive rice production systems of Southeast Asia. Initial lesions are pin-sized spots, often light yellow green to light orange (Fig. 1a). An older lesion appears as an orange spot with a stripe that advances toward the leaf tip (Fig. 1b). Lesions may become necrotic and coalesce, ultimately blighting the leaves. Although more common on leaves, red stripe lesions are also found on sheaths. Typical symptoms are usually observed from flowering to ripening.

Red stripe was first reported in 1988 from Indonesia (Mogi et al 1988). It also occurs in the Philippines (Barroga and Mew 1994), Malaysia (Yazid et al 1996), Thailand (Dhitikiattipong et al 1999), and Vietnam (Du et al 1991a). It has not yet been reported in temperate rice-growing countries. The disease is a potential threat to rice production in Southeast Asia, but a reliable quantification of yield losses has not been done yet.

Since red stripe symptoms do not resemble those caused by any known diseases of rice, various efforts have been exerted to understand its etiology. However, 12 years after red stripe was first reported, the causal organism has yet to be identified and its etiology remains obscure. To understand the etiology of red stripe, the most pressing questions that should be answered are the following: (1) Is red stripe caused by a biotic agent? (2) If so, what is the causal organism? (3) Is red stripe associated with production of toxins? and (4) How is the causal organism transmitted from one plant to another? This article reviews the hypotheses and results

* In this review, the term "disease" is defined as any disturbance of the plant that interferes with its normal growth and development (e.g., structure and function), economic value, or aesthetic quality and leads to the development of symptoms (Shurtleff and Averre 1997). A disease is caused by biotic or abiotic agents.

Fig. 1. Lesions of red stripe. A new lesion is a pin-sized spot (A), while an older lesion appears as a spot with a stripe that advances toward the leaf tip (B).

of studies that have been conducted to answer these questions. It also outlines the research work and other options that should be considered in the future to establish the etiology of red stripe. With this review, we hope to provide baseline information for current and future research on the etiology of red stripe and promote a better exchange of ideas among scientists working on this disease.

Is red stripe caused by a biotic agent?

Various observations and experimental results suggest that red stripe is caused by an infectious or biotic agent and not by an abiotic agent. The causal agent of red stripe can be transmitted from diseased to healthy plants placed together inside moist plastic cages. It has been observed that plants produce red stripe lesions when placed beside other plants with red stripe lesions (Suparyono 1999, Vinh et al 1999). Our experiments at IRRRI showed that healthy plants that are placed closer to plants with red stripe lesions have more diseased tillers than those placed farther away from diseased plants (Fig. 2). Experiments conducted at IRRRI and in Vietnam (Du et al 1991b) also showed that plants sprayed with fungicides have fewer red stripe lesions than the untreated check.

What is the causal organism?

The above information suggests that the causal agent of red stripe is transmissible from diseased to healthy rice plants. It is then very likely that the causal agent of red stripe is a biotic agent. Scientists have postulated various hypotheses with regard to the causal agent of red stripe. However, testing these hypotheses has been difficult because attempts to isolate the biotic agent using conventional methods in plant pathology have so far been unsuccessful.

To determine with certainty whether a particular biotic agent is the cause of a disease, it is necessary to critically examine

Fig. 2. Effect of distance from source (diseased) plants on the incidence of red stripe at different days after exposure during two trials (A and B). Each column represents the mean of five replications. In a given day after exposure, bars with the same letter are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ using the least significant difference test. Analyses were made on arcsine-transformed data. An experimental unit consisted of four healthy plants that were placed around a diseased plant at a given distance (10 to 25 cm). For the control, each of the four healthy plants was placed 10 cm away from another healthy plant.

its relationship with the host plant. Koch's postulates must be satisfied before a biotic agent can be regarded as a pathogen of red stripe. Koch's postulates state that (1) the suspected pathogen must always be present in the plant when the disease occurs; (2) the organism that is believed to cause the disease must be isolated and grown in pure culture on nutrient media (nonobligate parasites), or it must be grown on a susceptible host plant (obligate parasites); (3) the pure culture of the organism must produce symptoms or signs of the disease when inoculated on a healthy plant; and (4) the suspected causal organism must be reisolated in pure culture from the inoculated plant and must be identical to the organism initially isolated. Until the requirements of Koch's postulates are fulfilled, the causal agent remains obscure.

Below, we compare characteristics of pathogens that are suspected to cause red stripe with the general features of related

plant pathogens. Red stripe symptoms are also compared with typical symptoms of diseases caused by known plant pathogens.

Bacteria. Lesions caused by bacterial pathogens on plant leaf blades usually appear as spots, blight, streaks, or stripes in monocotyledonous plants. Pathogenic bacteria characteristically induce water-soaked lesions in infected tissues at initial stages. Bacterial ooze is usually formed from the cut edges of infected tissues.

Some reports indicate that red stripe could be caused by a bacterial pathogen. One of the first steps in determining whether red stripe is induced by a bacterial pathogen is the isolation and culture of bacteria from diseased tissues. Tuat (1999) isolated a bacterium from rice seedlings with typical red stripe symptoms. The bacterium was identified as *Acidovorax avenae* subsp. *avenae* (formerly *Pseudomonas avenae*) based on biochemical tests and fatty acid analysis. *A. avenae* subsp. *avenae* causes a common disease of rice known as bacterial brown stripe. However, the typical symptoms of bacterial brown stripe, which are brown, water-soaked stripes on the leaf blades and leaf sheaths (Webster and Gunnell 1992), differ from the symptoms of red stripe. The stripe extending from the spot of a red stripe lesion on the leaf blades is not water-soaked, and red stripe lesions are rarely observed on the sheath. Although bacterial brown stripe also occurs during the later development stages of the rice crop, it usually occurs during the seedling stage. In contrast, red stripe is normally observed during flowering to ripening stages. Furthermore, *A. avenae* subsp. *avenae* can be easily isolated and characterized (Shakya et al 1986). If it is indeed the causal organism of red stripe, Koch's postulates could have been easily fulfilled for red stripe. Unless red stripe is caused by a nonculturable bacterial species, the isolation and identification of the bacterium suspected to be the causal agent should not have been difficult. Until further evidence is provided, it remains unconfirmed if the isolate of *A. avenae* subsp. *avenae* obtained by Tuat (1999) is the causal agent of red stripe.

Recently, Kaku et al (2000) reported that white, transparent bacterial colonies were consistently isolated from all red stripe lesions of diseased leaf samples collected in Indonesia. Symptoms similar to red stripe developed on leaves of healthy plants that were inoculated with bacterial colonies using either the multineedle pricking method or infiltration method. They further reported that bacterial masses were also observed in the xylem vessels of diseased plants. The 16S rDNA sequence analysis of these isolates shows that the causal bacterium of red stripe is closely related to members of the genus *Microbacterium* (Kaku et al 2000). This study provides new information on the etiology of red stripe. However, lesions resulting from inoculation of rice leaves with the proposed causal organism do not seem to resemble typical red stripe lesions observed in the field. Furthermore, there is a need to determine whether the method described by Kaku et al (2000) will produce the same results in other laboratories and whether the isolate will produce symptoms resembling those that are typically produced by red stripe. At

IRRI, we have isolated several bacterial species from red stripe lesions using the isolation techniques and medium described by Kaku et al (2000). However, in two trials, we observed the predominance of yellow, shiny bacterial colonies in petri dishes. Pathogenicity tests by the pinpricking method showed that the isolated bacterial colonies did not produce red stripe symptoms. Modifying Kaku's method by forgoing surface sterilization of tissues produced white, transparent bacterial colonies. However, these colonies did not also produce red stripe symptoms in pathogenicity tests. At IRRI, we observed sections of red stripe lesions under the light and electron microscope, but we did not find bacteria-like organisms in the xylem. It is therefore necessary that other scientists repeat the isolation techniques described by Kaku et al (2000).

Some species of fastidious vascular bacteria (previously known as rickettsia-like organisms) are also pathogenic, but they cannot be grown on conventional culture media. Red stripe symptoms do not resemble typical symptoms of diseases caused by fastidious phloem-inhabiting bacteria (e.g., leaf stunting and clubbing, shoot proliferation, and greening of floral parts) or by fastidious xylem-inhabiting bacteria (e.g., necrosis of leaves and stunting of infected plants). So far, we have not observed these microorganisms or bacteria-like structures on red stripe lesions using the electron microscope.

Fungi. Fungal pathogens may cause local or systemic symptoms, such as general necrosis or death of plant tissues. They may also produce various structures on the surface of the host such as mycelium, sclerotia, and spores. Fungal pathogens are either facultative or obligate. Facultative fungal pathogens can be cultured and isolated using conventional laboratory techniques and their characteristics easily described. In contrast, obligate fungal pathogens cannot be cultured in artificial media, but they can be grown on a susceptible host plant and can produce typical symptoms. Koch's postulates should be satisfied even when dealing with obligate pathogens, although this is not always easy to do.

Red stripe lesions are, in many ways, similar to those of foliar diseases caused by some fungal pathogens. However, no fungal structures on infected tissues are visible to the naked eye. Several fungal species have been isolated from leaf tissues with red stripe lesions by plating small pieces of these leaf tissues on nutrient media (Du et al 1991a, Vinh 1997, Wakimoto et al 1998, Vinh et al 1999, Saad 1999). Among the fungi found were *Curvularia lunata*, *Nigrospora oryzae*, *Cercospora* sp., *Alternaria* spp., *Helminthosporium* spp., *Colletotrichum* spp., and *Fusarium* sp. None of these fungal isolates, however, produced typical red stripe lesions when rice leaves were inoculated with pure cultures. Most of these fungal species are saprophytes commonly associated with rice plants. We have also isolated these species from both red stripe lesions and healthy leaves by plating tissues on nonselective and selective media. Considering that the pathogen may be a slow-growing organism, we also attempted to induce sporulation in leaf tissues with red

stripe lesions in a moist chamber and exposed them to continuous light or near ultraviolet light. We then grew the spores that were collected from diseased leaves on nutrient media, but no isolate produced typical red stripe symptoms.

Experiments on the effect of fungicides on red stripe can be useful in establishing its etiology. These experiments can help determine whether red stripe is associated with a fungus even if it cannot be cultured on artificial media. The causal organism of red stripe could be a fungus if the application of certain fungicides is consistently effective against it. Du et al (1991b) reported that the severity of red stripe was lower in plants sprayed with benzimidazole fungicides, specifically benomyl and carbendazim, than in untreated plants. Experiments conducted at IRRRI showed that the intensity of red stripe was significantly lower in plants sprayed with benomyl than in plants sprayed with other chemicals (Fig. 3). In another study, we found that the rate of increase

in number of lesions and area under the number of lesions progress curve were significantly lower in diseased plants that were sprayed with benomyl than in those that were sprayed with water (see table). These results suggest that the causal organism of red stripe could be a fungus. Benzimidazole fungicides are systemic and have been widely used to control ascomycete (Keinath and Zitter 1998) and basidiomycete fungal plant pathogens. It is essential to conduct more tests on the efficacy of fungicides including those that specifically control fungal plant pathogens other than ascomycetes and basidiomycetes. Although certain groups of fungicides may be proven to be consistently effective against red stripe, further studies are necessary to confirm whether a fungicide or a group of fungicides has prevented the “causal fungus” from invading plant tissues. In plants that are already diseased, it is necessary to confirm whether the fungicide or the group of fungicides can inhibit the increase in number and size of lesions and the spread of red stripe to other plants.

Viruses, viroids, and mollicutes. Viruses and viroids usually cause yellowing and stunting of infected plants. Mollicutes, such as phytoplasmas (formerly known as mycoplasma-like organisms) (Sears and Kirkpatrick 1994, Fletcher et al 1998) and spiroplasmas, induce chlorosis, stunting of plants, and abnormal growth of plant parts. Culture or purification is not yet possible for some viruses and viroids. A few species belonging to the genus *Spiroplasma* can be cultured to comply with Koch’s postulates, but phytoplasmas and spiroplasmas are generally difficult to obtain from their host plants and vectors and culture on nutrient media. Their association with a disease may be confirmed by observations under the electron microscope and by transmission tests. The method of detecting plant viruses by rubbing or injecting healthy plants with sap from an infected plant has been tried but has produced negative results (Dhitikiattipong et al 1999, Vinh et al 1999). Thin sections of red stripe lesion tissues were examined under the transmission electron microscope but no virus-like particles were seen (H. Kaku as cited by Vinh et al 1999). Stunting or any abnormality in plant growth has never been observed even on plants with severe red stripe intensity. No evidence to date links insect vectors to the transmission of the causal agent of red stripe. In an experiment, Vinh et al (unpublished data) allowed the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* to feed on plants with red stripe lesions and placed the insects in cages with healthy plants. The severity of

Fig. 3. Effect of pesticides on the incidence of red stripe at different days after exposure of healthy plants to diseased plants during two trials (A and B). Each bar represents the mean of four replications. In a given day after exposure, columns with the same letter are not significantly different at $P \leq 0.05$ using the least significant difference test. Analyses were made on arcsine-transformed data. An experimental unit consisted of a diseased plant surrounded by four healthy plants.

Rate of increase in number of red stripe lesions and area under the number of lesions progress curve (AUNLPC) on plants sprayed with benomyl and water.^a

Treatment	Rate	AUNLPC (number-days) ^b
Water (control)	0.9804 a	398 a
Benomyl	-0.0031 b	59

^aMean of seven replications. Computations were based on data collected from 0 to 28 d after treatment application. In a column, means followed by different letters are significantly different at $P = 0.001$ using the least significant difference test. ^bAnalysis was based on log-transformed data.

red stripe did not significantly differ between cages with and without the brown planthopper. The involvement of other vectors in the transmission of the causal agent needs to be investigated. More detailed electron microscopy may reveal particles similar to viruses, viroids, or mollicutes. However, even if particles similar to these groups of pathogens are found, it will be necessary to prove that these particles are in fact causing red stripe.

Is red stripe associated with the production of toxins?

No studies have been conducted to test the hypothesis that a toxin is involved in red stripe development. The stripe emanating from the base of a red stripe lesion on the leaves may be due to a toxin produced by the causal organism. Since the stripe always advances toward the tips of leaves, the toxin is probably water-soluble and mobile within the xylem, and probably has a low molecular weight. To confirm whether the causal organism produces a toxin, filtrates from cultures of the causal agent or lesions should produce the stripe of a red stripe lesion on rice leaves. Future studies should also determine whether the causal organism can be isolated from the base of the lesion or from the stripe that extends toward the tips of leaves. If the causal organism can be isolated from the base of the lesion and not from the stripe, it can be assumed that the pathogen produces the toxin.

Fig. 4. Arrangement of infected and healthy plants inside a cage for multiplying diseased plants in a screenhouse. Red stripe lesions are observed on healthy plants starting from 2 to 3 wk after exposure to diseased plants. The cage is made of a wooden frame wrapped with polyethylene plastic sheet. The top of the cage has no cover to facilitate spraying of water.

Fig. 5. Layout of an experimental unit for studying the effect of plant spacing and chemicals on the intensity of red stripe.

What is the mode of transmission of the red stripe causal agent?

At IRRI, diseased plants were multiplied by placing 35- to 45-d-old healthy plants between infected plants (Fig. 4). The basic unit of the experiments, which were conducted at IRRI to determine factors affecting red stripe intensity, consisted of healthy plants placed around a diseased plant (Fig. 5). These plants were enclosed in cages and sprayed with water. After 2 to 3 wk of exposure, red stripe lesions were usually observed on healthy plants surrounding diseased plants. Our experiment showed that plants placed 10 and 15 cm away from plants with red stripe lesions have significantly more diseased tillers than those placed 20 and 25 cm away (Fig. 2). These observations and experiments suggest that tissue contacts facilitate the transmission of the causal agent. We also observed red stripe lesions on plants not in contact with diseased plants, although the level of red stripe incidence was lower than that on plants in contact with diseased plants (Fig. 4). Although these observations have raised several questions on the transmission of the causal agent, they suggest that transmission is possible even without tissue contacts.

Bacterial and fungal pathogens are usually disseminated by tissue contacts, wind, or water. Viruses and viroids are

transmitted by mechanical means through infected sap, insect vectors, or vegetative-propagating materials. Mollicutes are generally transmitted by insect vectors. However, there is no evidence that the vectors involved in the transmission of viruses, such as aphids, mites, planthoppers, and leafhoppers, or even parasitic fungi, are involved in the spread of red stripe. Although planthoppers and leafhoppers commonly occur in rice fields, no reports indicate that rice fields infected with red stripe have more planthoppers and leafhoppers than those without red stripe.

We investigated whether the causal agent of red stripe can be transmitted through the soil or seeds (Tisalona and Mew, unpublished data). Seeds of plants with red stripe lesions were collected in fields and then grown in pots containing soil that was collected from fields with severe red stripe intensity. The untreated check consisted of soil that was sterilized at about 150 °C for 4 h. We did not observe red stripe lesions on plants that grew on any of the treatments, which led to the suggestion that red stripe may not be associated with a soilborne or seedborne organism. Results also provided some evidence that abiotic factors associated with the soil may not be directly involved in red stripe disease. Our experiments at IRRI, as well as the information obtained from various workers, so far suggest that the causal organism of red stripe is transmitted from diseased to healthy plants. Further tests involving plants grown in soil collected from fields with severe red stripe intensity would provide evidence as to whether a soilborne organism is associated with the spread of the disease.

What are the next steps?

From all available information, except for the claims of Kaku et al (2000), the requirements of Koch's postulates have not been fulfilled for red stripe. Considering the difficulty in isolating the pathogen in pure culture, it is possible that compliance with Koch's postulates may not be achieved using conventional procedures. The causal agent of red stripe may be a fastidious organism requiring highly specific nutrients, an obligate pathogen, or some other so-called viable but nonculturable organism. It would be difficult to reintroduce such a pathogen as a pure culture into the plant and comply with Koch's postulates.

The tools of molecular plant pathology offer new approaches to identify the causal agent of red stripe. Among the options is the use of nucleic acid-based techniques, such as DNA hybridization and polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which have been useful in detecting and identifying several pathogens that are difficult or impossible to isolate. At IRRI, we are currently using arbitrary PCR primers that, among the multiple amplicons generated, consistently amplify a DNA fragment unique to tissues with red stripe lesions (and absent from healthy tissues). To prove that the unique fragment amplified from diseased tissues is indeed originating from the causal agent, experiments are needed to confirm whether the fragment hybridizes only to extracted DNA from diseased leaves and not to any arbitrary DNA sequence

present in rice leaves. Once sequence homology to DNA from diseased samples has been confirmed, the fragment will be used as a DNA probe to screen the collection maintained at the Entomology and Plant Pathology Division (IRRI) of characterized rice-associated bacteria (Cottyn et al 2001) and fungi to detect similarity to any of the described taxa. Further efforts will be conducted to isolate genomic DNA of the causal agent out of the DNA pool of diseased tissue by using the specific DNA fragment as bait (Henson and French 1993). If this is successful, the DNA of the causal agent can serve as a template to amplify the 16S rDNA gene that will provide phylogenetic information about the causal agent.

A complementary approach is a more detailed investigation of the effect of fungicides, bactericides, and antibiotics on red stripe development. Comparing the efficacy of benzimidazole fungicides with other groups of fungicides, bactericides, and antibiotics can help determine the causal organism of red stripe. Phytoplasmas and spiroplasmas are inhibited by tetracyclines but are resistant to penicillin, whereas fastidious vascular bacteria are sensitive to both tetracyclines and penicillin. Determining the effects of these antibiotics on red stripe development will help establish whether red stripe is caused by mollicutes or fastidious vascular bacteria. A thorough examination of cell sections from lesions under the transmission electron microscope would also be useful. The appearance of particles or masses under the electron microscope can give clues about the identity of the causal agent. It can also determine the occurrence of the causal agent inside the vascular system.

Further improvement of techniques for isolation, culture, and inoculation of the causal agent is necessary. The use of artificial media for fastidious and slow-growing organisms should be continuously explored. A primary consideration is the fact that several species of fungal endophytes are found on apparently healthy rice leaves (Fisher and Petrini 1992, Gonzales et al 2000). These endophytes can colonize internal plant tissues without causing apparent harm to their host and can thus live symptomlessly in the host for some time (Fisher and Petrini 1992). Similarly, several nonpathogenic bacterial species colonize rice plants as epiphytes. Thus, when applicable, isolates or tissues from diseased leaves should always be compared with those obtained from healthy plants of the same variety and age. These healthy plants should be collected from areas where red stripe does not occur because plants collected from areas favorable to red stripe development may appear healthy but may be latently infected by the pathogen. Epiphytes that are collected from leaves with red stripe lesions but not from healthy leaves may provide a clue about the biotic agent of red stripe. It should also be considered that the occurrence of microbial organisms might vary with the stage of lesion development.

Because of difficulties in isolating the causal agent of red stripe, it is possible that the causal agent is very slow-growing and obscured in culture by fast-growing saprophytic isolates. Iso-

lating suspected microorganisms from initial lesions should be considered because initial lesions may have fewer saprophytes and the pathogen may therefore grow better in vitro.

Since the stripe extending from the base of a red stripe lesion resembles the effect of a toxin, the compound that causes this stripe should be extracted, purified, and tested for the induction of red stripe lesions. Should a positive result be obtained, the purified chemical substance should be compared with known toxins of plant pathogens to help identify organisms producing it. Since toxins are mainly produced by either bacterial or fungal pathogens, a better understanding of the toxin may suggest the identity of the pathogen.

Finally, closer interaction among scientists working on red stripe is needed to speed up the research toward understanding the etiology of red stripe. Improved interaction would facilitate sharing of methodologies and approaches, such as formulation of nutrient media, methods for pathogenicity tests, multiplication of inoculum under controlled conditions, and assessment of disease intensity. It would also allow standardization of methods and better evaluation and comparison of results. A workshop held in March 1999, organized by IRRI and the Institute of Agricultural Sciences in South Vietnam, attempted to achieve these objectives. The interaction among scientists who participated in this workshop has resulted in the identification of new approaches and facilitated the exchange of ideas on the etiology of red stripe.

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